

NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF STRUCTURAL FILM ADHESIVES AND SCARF REPAIRS

Zhoucheng Su¹, Dan Wang¹, Huang Ming Chong², Zi An Wu², Feih Stefanie², and N. Sridhar^{1*}

¹ Department of Engineering Mechanics, Institute of High Performance Computing,
A*STAR Research Entities, 1 Fusionopolis Way, Singapore, 138632

² Joining Technology Group, Singapore Institute of Manufacturing Technology,
A*STAR Research Entities, 2 Fusionopolis Way, Singapore, 138634

* Corresponding author (narayanas@ihpc.a-star.edu.sg)

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ABSTRACT

With the wider application of composites, repairing damaged composite structures has become more important due to the high costs associated with full component replacement. Scarf repairs are drawing increasing attention since they provide not only a flush repair surface, but also high strength recovery. In this paper, both numerical and experimental studies are carried out for structural film adhesives and scarf repairs. A traction-separation law with bilinear softening is employed to simulate the bridging effect caused by the scrim in the adhesive layer for specimens in the double cantilever beam (DCB) configuration and has proved to match the test results better compared to conventional linear softening degradation laws. Progressive damage models are developed to virtually test both two dimensional (2D) and three dimensional (3D) scarf repairs with a [-45/90/45/0]_s lay-up under uniaxial tensile loading. For two dimensional (2D) scarf repairs, the experimental and numerical results show that the scarf angle has a significant influence on the fraction of the virgin laminate strength recovered. As the scarf angle increases, the fractional strength recovered is largely reduced. The damage mechanisms are examined in detail. It is also numerically found that the tensile strength increases as the offset between the parent and repair patches increases by up to one ply thickness. Numerical results for the 3D scarf repair also agree with the experimental results. The computationally efficient numerical framework developed in this study can be used to virtually design and optimize scarf joints and minimize the number of real, but expensive, physical tests.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recent advances in composite and lightweight material technologies have led to increasing applications of adhesively bonded structures and repairs in aerospace, automotive, and marine and offshore industries. The adhesively bonded joint transfers load from one component to another and must be designed to satisfy structural requirements. Aircraft manufacturers also request adhesive bonding as per structural repair manual for the repair of primary carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) components in new generation aircraft, such as Boeing 787. For repair processes, structural adhesives are generally provided in the solid film form with scrim carriers to facilitate the handling and bonding procedure. In numerical modelling, the bonding adhesives or interfaces between composite plies are usually represented by cohesive zone models in the form of traction-separation laws. The traction separation laws can be directly measured using double cantilever beam (DCB) and end-notched flexure (ENF) tests by differentiating the J -integral obtained from tests with respect to the corresponding crack-tip separation [1-3].

In the usage of composite structures, inevitable damage occurs due to mechanical loading or environmental conditions [4]. Composite damage is not always visible to the naked eye, and may extend from the surface to the inside. Thus, composite repairs are considerably more complicated than metal structure repairs. Scarf repairs are a preferred way because of the repair efficiency, resulting flush aerodynamic surfaces and the emulated structural stiffness of the parent laminate because of ply-to-ply matching [5,6]. Scarf repairs in composite laminates are however complicated because of multiple failure modes, such as fibre fracture, matrix cracking, interlaminar delamination and adhesive

The mode I traction-separation law is obtained via direct measurement using DCB tests, as given by the black line in Fig. 2. It is clearly seen that there is a long tail accounting for about 20~30% of the total fracture toughness in the traction-separation law, which is commonly indicating a bridging effect. This bridging effect normally happens in composite adherends with fibers pulled from the composite resin system bridging at the crack tip to delay the brittle fracture event [10]. Here, a similar effect is caused by the scrim support in form of a polyester knit in the adhesive layer, as shown in Fig. 3, which is used to improve the handling qualities and to control the bondline thickness. Thus, our traction-separation law is numerically simplified with a more accurate bilinear softening, instead of the commonly used linear softening, as illustrated in Fig. 2. Both the linear and bi-linear softening laws are created in such a way that the fracture toughness (area under the curve) is equal to the experimental results.

(a) The full traction-separation law (b) The tail of the traction-separation law
 Figure 2: Mode I traction-separation law obtained from direct experimental measurement.

Figure 3: Illustration of the scrim in the adhesive layer.

The load-displacement curves of the finite element models with both linear and bilinear softening are given in Fig. 4. The test result is also provided for comparison. It is shown that using the finite element model with the bilinear softening cohesive law can match the experimental results well. Using a linear softening cohesive law overestimates the maximum bearing capacity.

Figure 4: Comparison of load-displacement curves (DCB)

3 2D AND 3D SCARF REPAIRS

3.1 Experimental setup

Both 2D scarf repairs/lap joints and 3D scarf repairs are investigated numerically and experimentally. 2D scarf repairs with three different scarf angles (2° , 5° , and 10°) are investigated. The scarf repairs are subjected to uniaxial tension tests. 3D scarf repairs with 2° scarf angle are tested under uniaxial tensile loading as well. In general, the parent laminate is machined to a prescribed angle by milling and then cleaned with acetone prior to bonding. The hard repair patch is machined similarly and is then bonded onto the parent laminate, as illustrated in Fig. 5. Due to the finite thickness of the film adhesive (same thickness as a composite ply), manufacturing hard patch scarf repairs on a flat tool surface generally leads to a ply offset as illustrated in Fig. 5(a). Hence special care is taken to minimize any uneven overlap of the film adhesive during the curing set-up by extending the film adhesive under the other side as illustrated in Fig. 5(b). However, it is found that the offset cannot be eliminated completely. A similar methodology is applied for the 3D repair geometry as shown in Figs. 5(c) and (d). Here, hard patches are cut and machined from the same autoclaved laminates as the substrate materials.

Figure 5: Repair specimen geometries.

The 2D scarf lap joint repair specimens are manufactured as large panels, which are then cut into rectangular strips of 25 mm width by waterjet cutting. Glass fibre end tabs are then attached using a toughened epoxy adhesive (Araldite 2015). The repair strength is then tested under tensile loading conditions on an Instron 5982. At least 5 specimens are tested for the 2D scarf repair specimens for the various repair configurations. For the 3D repair test specimens, carbon fibre end tabs are attached using a toughened epoxy adhesive (Araldite 2015). A special fixture for load transfer to the Instron

machine is designed via multiple screws in each tab area [11]. The repair strength is then tested under tensile loading conditions on a 150 ton Instron universal testing machine.

3.2 Numerical modelling

Progressive damage models are developed following the work by Su et al. [12]. For the scarf geometry, 3D solid elements are used to model the composite plies instead of using continuum shell elements as in Su et al.'s work [12]. Three dimensional (3D) Hashin criteria [13] consisting of criteria for fiber tensile failure, fiber compressive failure, matrix tensile failure and matrix compressive failure, are employed to trigger damage in the composite lamina and the subsequent propagation is governed by energy-based linear softening for the different damage modes. Interlaminar delamination between plies with different orientations are modelled using the commonly used bilinear cohesive element model. The adhesive bonding is also modelled using the cohesive element model. All material models are implemented as user-defined material (UMAT) models in ABAQUS [14]. For detailed formulation the reader is referred to references [12] and [13].

Typical FE models for 2D and 3D scarf repair configurations are shown in Fig. 6(a) and (b), respectively. The mesh with the refinement around the scarf region is generated using an automated in-house script. For the 2D scarf repairs, the mesh is generated for the front surface and then extruded to form the mesh for the actual repairs. For the 3D scarf repairs, the mesh in the central region is generated by rotating the surface mesh. The region away from the central region can be regularly meshed. The lay-up of the composite plate is $[45/90/-45/0]_s$ and the ply thickness is 0.2 mm, which yields the total thickness of about 1.6 mm.

Figure 6: Illustrations of FE models for scarf repairs.

The material properties are given in Table 2. In this table, E_{11} , E_{22} , E_{33} , G_{12} , G_{13} , G_{23} , ν_{12} , ν_{13} , and ν_{23} are the elastic constants of the composite lamina. The subscripts 1, 2, and 3 denote fiber direction, in-plane transverse direction, and thickness direction, respectively. X_t and X_c are the tensile strength and compressive strength along fiber direction. Y_t and Y_c are the tensile strength and compressive strength along the transverse directions. S_{12} and S_{23} are the in-plane shear strength and out-of-plane shear strength, respectively. G_{fc}^t and G_{fc}^c are translaminar fracture toughnesses for tensile and compressive loadings. G_{nc} and G_{sc} are the fracture toughnesses for mode I and mode II

damage in the transverse direction. For the cohesive element model, K_N , K_S , and K_T are the penalty stiffness constants for mode I, mode II and mode III respectively, N , S , and T are the corresponding strengths, and G_{Ic} , G_{IIc} , and G_{IIIc} are the corresponding fracture energies.

Lamina properties	$E_{11} = 139.0$ GPa; $E_{22} = E_{33} = 8.32$ GPa; $G_{12} = G_{13} = 4.6$ GPa; $G_{23} = 4.2$ GPa; $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.32$; $\nu_{23} = 0.42$; $X_t = 2169$ MPa; $X_c = 1504$ MPa; $Y_t = 57$ MPa; $Y_c = 120$ MPa; $S_{12} = 90$ MPa; $S_{23} = 90$ MPa; $G_{fc}^t = 112.7$ * kJ/m ² ; $G_{fc}^c = 51.8$ kJ/m ² ; $G_{nc} = 0.667$ kJ/m ² ; $G_{sc} = 2.93$ kJ/m ²
Cohesive properties for interlaminar interface	$K_N = 1200$ GPa; $K_S = K_T = 430$ GPa; $N = 55$ MPa; $S = T = 85$ MPa; $G_{Ic} = 0.667$ kJ/m ² ; $G_{IIc} = G_{IIIc} = 2.93$ kJ/m ²
Cohesive parameters for adhesive (0.2 mm)	$K_N = 3.6$ GPa; $K_S = K_T = 1.8$ GPa; $N = 24$ MPa; $S = T = 36$ MPa; $G_{Ic} = 0.8$ kJ/m ² ; $G_{IIc} = G_{IIIc} = 1.91$ kJ/m ²

Table 2: Lamina properties and cohesive parameters for interlaminar interface and adhesive.

3.3 Results and discussions of 2D scarf repairs

Fig. 7 shows the stress-strain curve comparisons between experiments and FE simulations (with offset between repair patch and the parent laminate) for different scarf angles. FE simulations and experiments show that the scarf repair strength decreases as the scarf angles increases. It is also seen that the strength of the scarf repair increases as the offset increases from 0.0 mm to 0.2 mm. In general, the curves from FE simulations with perfect alignment of patch and parent laminate plies show some differences compared to the experimental curves. But for each scarf angle, one of the three simulations with different offset shows very good agreement with experimental results. It should be noted that the experimental results show the expected scatter in results due to uncertainties arising from the manufacturing conditions, hence influencing the final scarf geometry.

Figure 7: Comparisons of stress-strain curves between experiments and simulations with different offsets for different scarf angles (lay-up [-45/90/45/0]_s).

The damage patterns of the different scarf repairs are examined in detail, as shown in Figs. 8-10. Fig. 8 shows the adhesive failure for the specimens with different scarf angles. The failure in the adhesive is similar for the different scarf angles. The adhesive failure starts from central region connecting the zero plies on the parent and repair patch and then propagates towards the top and

bottom along the scarf until it reaches the 90° plies. At this point matrix failure starts to occur and significant load reduction is predicted.

Figure 8: Comparison of adhesive failure in the specimens with different scarf angles.

The matrix failure at the end of simulations is shown in Fig 9. It is seen that there is extensive damage in the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies and 90° plies for 2° scarf repair. In comparison, moderate matrix failure is observed in the 5° scarf repair and little matrix failure is found in the 10° scarf repair. The ultimate load increases for a smaller scarf angle, resulting in enhanced matrix failure.

Figure 9: Comparison of matrix failure in the specimens with different scarf angles.

For all scarf angles, there is very little interlaminar delamination. This is mainly because the interfaces are much stronger than the adhesive for this particular material system with toughened interfaces. Fiber failure is only observed for the 2° scarf repair. It occurs at the tips of Ply 3 and Ply 4&5. Upon checking the damage history, we find that the adhesive failure accumulates until it becomes catastrophic. Only then the stresses in the fiber direction within the tips of Ply 3 and Ply 4&5 increase drastically, leading to fiber failure in these plies. But for 5° and 10° scarf repairs, the fiber direction stress cannot reach the ultimate strength of the lamina along the fiber direction before complete failure of the adhesive layer occurs.

Figure 10: Fiber failure in the 2° scarf repair.

As concluded above, the scarf strength increases as the offset increases from 0.0 mm to 0.2 mm for a given scarf angle. To determine the cause of this phenomenon, we examined the distribution of the stress components (and especially the S_{13} component) in the adhesive for the three different alignments for the 2° scarf angle. Fig. 10 shows the contours of S_{13} for the three cases. It is seen that the stress level is lower as the offset increases. More importantly, the region of negative S_{13} becomes larger as the offset increases. It means that the adhesive is more effectively deformed to bear the load transferred for larger ply offsets, and this leads to higher scarf strength.

Figure 10: Comparison of stress contours (S_{13}) between scarf repairs with different offsets.

3.4 Results and discussions of 3D scarf repairs

We further extended the work to three dimensional (3D) scarf repairs. Based on the findings of 2D scarf repairs, the study on full 3D scarf repairs focused on the 2° case only. The stress-strain curve predicted by the progressive damage model is compared to those obtained from experiments as shown in Fig. 11. It is shown that the predicted stiffness of the repaired panel agrees very well with the experimental results, and the predicted repair strength is in a good agreement with experimental values as well.

Figure 11. Comparison of nominal stress-strain curves of 3D scarf repairs with $[-45/90/45/0]_s$ lay-up.

The predicted damage patterns are summarized and compared with the experimental observations in Fig. 12. It should be noted that damage is suppressed in regions away from the scarf region. It is clearly seen that the adhesive failure is mainly driven by the stress component S_{13} at locations connecting the zero degree plies. Extensive matrix damage is predicted in both parent laminate and the

repair patch. This is similar to the matrix damage observed in the experiments as shown in Fig. 12. Fiber failure is found to initiate mostly in the zero degree plies. Fiber failure starts from the upper and lower edges (perpendicular to the loading direction) of the hole in the zero degree plies. When the fiber failure further propagates, the panel is therefore expected to break at either the upper or lower edge across the whole specimen, resulting in unsymmetrical breakage of the specimen away from the centre line. This phenomenon is evident for all the tested panels, of which one is shown in Fig.12.

Figure 12: Damage in the 3D scarf repair with $[-45/90/45/0]_s$ lay-up under uniaxial tension (loading along x direction for the FE simulation)

4 CONCLUSIONS

Structural film adhesive with scrims and scarf repairs with different configurations were studied. DCB tests of aluminum plates bonded by the Henkel PL7000 adhesive show significant bridging effect due to the scrims inside of the adhesive film. This bridging effect was modelled by a cohesive element model with bilinear softening. Progressive damage models were then developed to predict the damage progression and scarf strength for both 2D and 3D scarf repairs. Systematic experimental testing was carried out to validate the models and to identify the damage mechanisms and effect of the different parameters on the scarf strength. It is found that the models developed in this study accurately predict the scarf strength and damage propagation for scarf repairs with different offset and scarf angle configurations. The 2D scarf repair study shows that the scarf strength decreases as the scarf angle increases. One particular finding is that the strength of 2D scarf repair increases with increasing offset between the parent laminate and the repair patch for up to one ply thickness. The models serve as a useful virtual tool for design and optimization of scarf repairs.

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